

Climate Change: Occupational Safety and Health

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Be Aware

Climate change refers to significant and long-term alterations in the Earth's climate patterns, including temperature, precipitation, wind patterns, and other atmospheric conditions. These changes are primarily driven by human activities, such as the burning of fossil fuels (coal, oil, and natural gas), deforestation, industrial processes, and agricultural practices, which release greenhouse gases (GHGs) into the atmosphere. The primary greenhouse gases responsible for climate change include carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), nitrous oxide (N₂O), and fluorinated gases. These gases trap heat in the Earth's atmosphere, leading to a gradual increase in global temperatures, a phenomenon known as global warming.

Figure 1

Role of Humanity in Climate Change

Note. The picture taken from Kantipur explains the reality and status of climate change.

Climate change is a significant contributor to the alarming levels of air pollution in Nepal, which has been ranked as the most polluted country in the world by IQAir's recent direct update on April 7th (Chaitra 27th). This is a consequence of climate change that has been unfolding over the past few decades. Nepal is partly responsible for this situation, while other countries also play a role.

The impact of this pollution is devastating for human health, the environment, and all living species. According to the Ministry of Health and Population, air

pollution claims the lives of 42,100 Nepalis annually, with 19% being children under five and 27% being elderly individuals aged 70 and above. This has reduced the average life expectancy of Nepalis by 4.1 years. The statistics clearly show that air pollution is a leading cause of death in Nepal.

Global temperatures have risen by about 2.0 degrees Fahrenheit (1.1 degrees Celsius) since the late 19th century, primarily due to human-caused emissions of carbon dioxide (CO₂) and other greenhouse gases. This warming trend has accelerated in recent decades, with each of the last three decades being successively warmer than any preceding decade since 1850. Most of the warming occurred in the past 35 years, with 16 of the 17 warmest years on record occurring since 2001. The year 2016 stands out as the warmest year recorded. (<https://www.epa.gov/climatechange-science/impacts-climate-change>)

The effects of this global warming are already being felt across the planet. Sea levels have risen by about 8 inches in the last century due to the expansion of warmer oceans and the melting of ice sheets and glaciers. The oceans have also become more acidic as they absorb excess CO₂ from the atmosphere. Additionally, snow cover has decreased in many regions, and glaciers are retreating at an alarming rate.

These changes in the Earth's climate system are having far-reaching consequences for ecosystems, economies, and human health and well-being. Urgent action is needed to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and mitigate the worst impacts of climate change.

<https://www.nationalgeographic.com/environment/article/global-warming-effects>

Impact of Climate Change

Climate change poses unique challenges to occupational health and safety in developing countries due to factors such as limited resources, infrastructure vulnerabilities, and socioeconomic disparities.

Heat Stress and Indoor Work Environments: Many workers in developing countries are employed in industries such as agriculture, manufacturing, and construction, where they may be exposed to high temperatures and humidity. Inadequate ventilation, lack of air conditioning, and limited access to clean drinking

water exacerbate the risk of heat stress and heat-related illnesses. Additionally, workers in indoor environments without proper cooling systems, such as factories and warehouses, may also be at risk.

Agricultural Sector Vulnerability. Agricultural workers in developing countries are particularly vulnerable to the impacts of climate change. Changes in temperature and precipitation patterns can affect crop yields, water availability, and the spread of pests and diseases, impacting farmers' livelihoods and health. Exposure to agrochemicals and strenuous labor further compound the risks to agricultural workers' health and safety.

Extreme Weather Events. Developing countries are often more susceptible to the impacts of extreme weather events such as hurricanes, floods, and droughts. These events can disrupt livelihoods, damage infrastructure, and result in injuries or fatalities among workers involved in sectors such as construction, transportation, and emergency response. Limited resources for disaster preparedness and response exacerbate the challenges faced by workers in these contexts.

Air Pollution and Respiratory Health. Developing countries often experience high levels of air pollution from sources such as industrial emissions, vehicle exhaust, and biomass burning. Poor air quality can exacerbate respiratory conditions such as asthma and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) among workers, particularly those in urban areas or industries with high pollution levels.

Limited Access to Healthcare and Protective Equipment. Workers in developing countries may have limited access to healthcare services, occupational health clinics, and personal protective equipment (PPE), further compromising their ability to address and mitigate occupational health risks associated with climate change. This lack of resources can result in higher rates of workplace injuries, illnesses, and fatalities.

Vector-Borne Diseases. Climate change can influence the distribution and prevalence of vector-borne diseases such as malaria, dengue fever, and Zika virus, particularly in tropical and subtropical regions. Workers in sectors such as agriculture, forestry, and waste management may face an increased risk of exposure to these diseases due to changes in vector habitats and breeding patterns.

Challenges for Outdoor Workers. Outdoor workers, such as agricultural workers, construction

workers, and utility maintenance workers, are particularly vulnerable to the effects of climate change due to prolonged exposure to extreme temperatures, UV radiation, and weather-related hazards. Heat stress, dehydration, sunburn, and injuries from extreme weather events pose significant risks to their health and safety.

Impact on Occupational Hygiene and Ergonomics. Climate change can affect occupational hygiene and ergonomics by altering work environments, indoor air quality, and ergonomic conditions. Changes in temperature, humidity, and air circulation may affect thermal comfort, productivity, and the risk of musculoskeletal disorders among workers.

Climate Change(CC). Social and environmental determinants of health (clean air, safe drinking water, sufficient food and secure water).

Between 2030 and 2050, (250 000 additional deaths per year, are expected from malnutrition, malaria, diarrheal, and heat stress.

The direct damage cost to health is estimated to be between US\$ 2-4 billion/year by 2030.

Areas with weak health infrastructure – mostly in developing countries – will be least able to cope without assistance to prepare and respond.

Figure 2

How Climate Change Can Affect Us

Climate change is significantly impacting the water sources in Bangladesh, particularly in coastal areas, leading to increased salinity levels in drinking water. This has severe implications for the health of pregnant women, who are more susceptible to the effects of high salt intake.

Salinity in Drinking Water. Rising sea levels, cyclones, and storm surges are causing saltwater intrusion into freshwater sources, contaminating drinking water in coastal Bangladesh.

Impact on Pregnant Women. High salt intake from contaminated drinking water has been linked to increased blood pressure and urinary protein excretion, progressive kidney disease, pre-eclampsia, and gestational hypertension in pregnant women.

Health Risks. Consuming saline water during pregnancy can lead to worsened maternal and fetal outcomes, including impaired liver function, low platelet count, intrauterine growth retardation, preterm birth, and maternal and perinatal deaths.

Seasonal Patterns. The dry season is particularly critical, as salt intake from drinking water is significantly higher during this period, exacerbating hypertension in pregnancy.

Lack of Research. Despite the pressing issue, there is a lack of data on the specific impact of high salt intake on pregnant women in Bangladesh, highlighting the need for further research and intervention. (<https://earthjournalism.net/stories/is-climate-change-impacting-the-reproductive-health-of-women-in-coastal-bangladesh>)

Figure 3

Effect of Climate Change on Pregnant Women in Bangladesh

<https://www.icrw.org/qa-navigating-the-climate-crisis-unraveling-the-impact-water-salinity-on-maternal-health/>

Despite Having the Highest Sodium Levels, Tube Well are the Most Common Source of Drinking Water in the Village

A Pond with Lower Salinity Level that Villagers in Dacope use to College Water for Drinking and Cooking

Climate Change and Digital Transformation

The linkage between climate change and digital transformation is complex, with both opportunities and challenges. Digital technologies can play a significant role in addressing climate change challenges, but they also contribute to greenhouse gas emissions and environmental degradation.

Opportunities

- Digital technologies can help reduce energy consumption, environmental impact, and greenhouse gas emissions through efficiency gains and optimizing resource use.
- Artificial Intelligence (AI), the Internet of Things (IoT), cloud computing, and other digital solutions have the potential to accelerate and maximize the effects of environmental policies.
- Digitalization of various sectors, such as agriculture, buildings management, and energy, can contribute to resource optimization and a more sustainable future.

Challenges

- The digital sector itself needs to embrace sustainability and become a sector that saves resources, increases efficiency, and allows for product reparability and reuse.
- All the devices we use daily, data centers, and communication infrastructures consume increasing amounts of energy and materials, contributing to climate degradation.
- The use of critical raw materials in electronic devices is constantly increasing, and meeting global climate goals will rely on these materials, which have a significant carbon footprint.
- There is a lack of data and linkages at the policy level between digital technology use and climate adaptation, which limits comprehensive evaluations of key enablers for using digital technologies to adapt to climate change.

Figure 8

Ambivalence of the Choice of Humanity

Occupational health services

The ILO/ WHO combinedly defines “occupational health services” as services entrusted with essentially preventive functions and responsible for advising the employer, the workers, and their representatives in the undertaking on the requirements for establishing and maintaining a safe and healthy working environment which will facilitate optimal physical and mental health concerning work and the adaptation of work to the capabilities of workers in the light of their state of physical and mental health. (Rantanen & Fedotov, 1995).

It encompasses a wide range of disciplines, regulations, policies, and practices aimed at preventing work-related injuries, illnesses, and fatalities, as well as promoting a safe and healthy work environment for all employees.

Occupational safety and health a key elements in achieving sustained decent working conditions and

strong preventive safety cultures. Close to 80 percent of all ILO standards and instruments are either wholly or partly concerned with issues related to occupational safety and health.

Minimizing the Effect of Climate Change

Risk Assessment and Management. Conduct comprehensive risk assessments to identify climate-related hazards in the workplace, such as heat stress, extreme weather events, and air pollution. Develop and implement risk management plans to mitigate these hazards, including measures such as engineering controls, administrative controls, and personal protective equipment (PPE).

Heat Stress Prevention. Implement heat stress prevention programs that include measures such as providing shaded rest areas, access to cool drinking water, and scheduling work tasks during cooler times of the day. Train workers and supervisors on recognizing the signs and symptoms of heat-related illnesses and how to respond effectively.

Emergency Preparedness and Response. Develop emergency preparedness and response plans to address climate-related emergencies such as hurricanes, floods, wildfires, and extreme heat events. Ensure that workers are trained in emergency procedures and have access to necessary resources, such as first aid kits and evacuation routes.

Training and Education. Provide workers with training and education on climate-related risks and how to protect themselves from hazards in the workplace. This includes training on the proper use of PPE, safe work practices in extreme weather conditions, and recognizing early warning signs of climate-related health effects.

Infrastructure and Work Environment Design. Design and retrofit workplaces to withstand climate-related hazards, such as building structures that can withstand extreme weather events and providing adequate ventilation and cooling systems to reduce heat exposure. Consider climate resilience factors in the design and construction of new infrastructure and buildings.

Health Surveillance and Monitoring. Implement health surveillance and monitoring programs to track and assess the impacts of climate-related hazards on workers' health. This includes monitoring for heat-related illnesses, respiratory conditions, and vector-borne diseases, as well as providing access to healthcare services for affected workers.

Community and Stakeholder Engagement.

Engage with local communities, stakeholders, and relevant government agencies to develop collaborative approaches to addressing climate-related risks in the workplace. This may involve participating in community resilience initiatives, sharing best practices, and advocating for policy changes to support climate adaptation and mitigation efforts.

Promotion of Sustainable Practices. Promote sustainable work practices that reduce greenhouse gas emissions and minimize the contribution to climate change. This may include initiatives such as energy conservation, waste reduction, and transitioning to renewable energy sources to create healthier and more resilient workplaces.

Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) & Climate Change; Goals to 2030

- Goal 3.3 End the epidemic of AIDS, tuberculosis malaria, and neglect tropical diseases and combat hepatitis, water-borne disease, and other communicable disease.
- Goal 3.9 substantially reduces the number of deaths and illnesses from hazardous chemicals and air, water, and soil pollution and contamination.
- Goal 6.1 -Achieve universal and equitable access to safe and affordable drinking water for all.
- Goal 6.5- Implement integrated water resources management at all levels, including through transboundary cooperation as appropriate.
- Goal 6.6- Protect and restore water-related ecosystems, including mountains, forests, wetlands, rivers, revolute, and lakes.
- Goal 7.4 – Enhance International cooperation to facilitate access to lean energy research and technology, including renewable energy, energy efficiency, and advanced and cleaner fossil-fuel technology, and promote investment in energy infrastructure and clean energy technology
- Global 13.1 Strengthen resilience and adaptive capacity to climate-related hazards and natural disasters in all countries
- Goal 13.2 Integrate climate change measures into national policies, strategies and planning
- Goal 13.3 Improve education, awareness-raising –raising and human and institutional capacity on climate change mitigation, adaptation, impact reduction, and early warning.
- Goal 13.5 Promote mechanisms for raising capacity for effective climate change-related planning and management least developed

countries and small island developing States, including women, youth, and local and marginalized communities

- Goal 15.2 Promote the implantation of suitable management of all types of forests, halt deforestation, restore degraded forests and substantially increase afforestation and forestation globally.
- Goal 15.3 Combat desertification, restore degraded land and soil, including land affected by desertification, drought, and floods, and strive to achieve a land degradation-neutral world
- Nepal’s Vulnerability & adaptation Assessment of CC (disease & health risks-GoV. of Nepal 2022)

Climate sensitive disease (CSDs) of Nepal (2004 – 2020)

- Seven vector-borne diseases (malaria, kala-azar, Japanese encephalitis, scrub typhus, dengue, zika, chikungunya)
- Two food and water-borne diseases (cholera and acute gastroenteritis)
- One respiratory disease (severe acute respiratory infections)
- Two other climate-sensitive diseases (undernutrition and mental illness)
- Terai region cases of malaria 64% and Kala-azar 94%
- Hill region cases dengue 52% and scrub typhus 44%
- In Terai infections influenza 43% and Severe Acute Respiration illness (SARI) 44% were observed (Ministry of Health and Population, 2022).

Figure 9
Can We Have...?

Mishra, A. K. (2024, April 7)

Kindly be assured that any specific guideline has not been followed and all pictures are adopted only. Thanks to all of them whose pictures and contents might have referred with a view to create awareness.

Neuralink's Quest to Integrate Technology with the Human Brain

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Introduction

Neuralink Corp. is an American neurotechnology company developing implantable brain-computer interfaces (BCIs). Based in Fremont, California, as of 2024, Neuralink was founded by Elon Musk and a team of seven scientists and engineers. The company was launched in 2016 and first publicly reported in March 2017. Neuralink develops implantable chips and electronics to record and stimulate the brain. The company states its goals as treating serious brain diseases in the short term and eventually achieving human enhancement, sometimes called transhumanism. They have successfully secured \$158 million in funding and had a team of around 90 people as of July 2019. In May 2023, after four years, they received approval from the FDA to conduct the first human trials for their BCI chip.

Figure 1

The Process of Implanting N1 Chip on the Brain

The history of brain-computer interfaces (BCIs) starts with Hans Berger's discovery of the electrical activity of the human brain and the development of electroencephalography (EEG). In 1924, Berger was the first to record human brain activity using EEG. In 1969, operant conditioning studies by Fetz and colleagues at the Regional Primate Research Center and Department of Physiology and Biophysics at the University of Washington School of Medicine in Seattle showed for the first time that monkeys could learn to control the deflection of a biofeedback meter arm with neural activity. Similar work in the 1970s established that monkeys could quickly learn to voluntarily control the firing rates of individual and multiple neurons in the primary motor cortex if they were rewarded for generating appropriate patterns of neural activity. Since the mid-1990s, there has been rapid development in BCIs. Several groups have been able to capture complex brain motor cortex signals by recording from

neural ensembles (groups of neurons) and using these to control external devices.

What is the Brain?

Before learning about Neuralink and its BCI technology, we need to answer the obvious question: "What is the brain, and how does it work?" In simple terms, our brain is a naturally occurring electronic device. Every single action we take comes from our brain sending electrical signals through our nervous system to various parts of our body.

What is the Mind?

The mind is what the brain does and how it functions. According to Canadian-American cognitive psychologist and popular science author Steven Pinker, the mind is "a system of organs of computation designed by natural selection to solve the kinds of problems our ancestors faced in their foraging way of life. In particular, understanding and outmaneuvering objects, animals, plants, and other people." This concept is also known as the computational theory of mind. In this sense, the human mind is quite similar to that of a robot. It processes information through the connections between neurons. The mind perceives information as a configuration of symbols, and by connecting these symbols to other symbols in the mind or to neurons that control muscles, behavior is created.

Mission and Vision of Neuralink

Neuralink aims to create a generalized brain interface to restore autonomy to those with unmet medical needs today and unlock human potential tomorrow. Neuralink seeks to address neurological disorders, revolutionize healthcare, and enhance human capabilities. By developing high-bandwidth brain-machine interfaces (BMIs), the project aims to treat conditions such as paralysis and diseases like Alzheimer's and Parkinson's. Additionally, Elon Musk believes that by merging with AI, humans can keep pace with rapid technological advancements and potentially achieve symbiosis with artificial intelligence.

What is an N1 Chip and How Does It Work?

The N1 chip serves as the central processing unit (CPU) of the Neuralink system. Analogous to a computer's CPU, it's the thinking hub responsible for critical tasks. The N1 chip gathers the electrical signals emitted by the brain, processes them into a usable format, and transmits them for external devices to interpret. In essence, it acts as the translator between the brain's complex language and the digital world. By inserting electrodes into the brain that can record and send pulses of electricity and connecting those electrodes to a chip that can relay information to and from the brain, we can effectively restore and even enhance our existing brain function. The N1 chip can cut out the middleman, allowing us to directly control any system without additional instruments. It's like controlling a system directly just by thinking.

Process of Implanting the N1 Chip

The threads of the implant are so fine that they can't be inserted by the human hand. For this purpose, Neuralink developed a surgical robot called R1, which is designed to reliably and efficiently insert these threads exactly where they need to be. The robot head contains the optics and sensors of five camera systems and the optics for an optical coherence tomography (OCT) system. The needle, which is thinner than a human hair, grasps, inserts, and releases threads.

Who It's For

According to Neuralink, they are currently focused on giving people with quadriplegia the ability to control their computers and mobile devices with their thoughts.

Animal Testing Controversies

Neuralink first tested its technology on animals after inking a deal with the University of California to test its brain chip at UC Davis's primate center. These clinical trials reportedly killed around 1,500 animals, including primates and pigs, since 2018, according to Reuters. Neuralink terminated its agreement with UC Davis in 2020, but animals reportedly continued to die during experiments held in internal departments. In August 2020, Neuralink demonstrated brain activity in a chip-implanted pig. Less than a year later, the company showed how a chip-implanted monkey played Pong. The FDA dismissed Neuralink's application for human trials in 2022, citing the potential for the implant's threads to migrate to other areas of the brain, according to Reuters. Later, in May 2023, Musk announced that Neuralink received FDA approval.

Figure 2

First Successful Trial on Animal Brain

First Successful Animal Trial

Neuralink unveiled a new video of a nine-year-old monkey named "Pager" playing Pong with its brain. The three-minute video shows Pager learning to control a computer with his brain activity. At first, the monkey uses a joystick to interact with the computer for a "tasty banana smoothie, delivered through a straw." The narrator states that Pager has two Neuralink devices implanted in his brain. The devices, which Musk calls a "Fitbit for your skull," were revealed at a press briefing in August 2020. As Pager plays through the games, the narrator explains that the Neuralink devices in his brain are reading his brain activity and that activity is being decoded by a computer. When the team disconnects the joystick, Pager keeps playing the game—and the brain implant allows him to play "MindPong," as Neuralink has dubbed it.

First Successful Human Trial

Figure 3

Trial on the Human Brain

Noland Arbaugh (P1) is one of the first people with the Neuralink implantation in his brain. He was a student at Texas A&M University in College Station, and while working as a counselor at a children's camp, he suffered a freak accident that left him paralyzed. With the help of Neuralink, he can now control electronics without any physical contact, just using his brain. In the early days after the N1 chip implantation, Noland could be seen playing chess and Mario Kart using only his brain.

Pros

Improved Ability to Learn and Remember New Information. Neuralink technology has the potential to enhance human intelligence by establishing a direct connection between our brains and computers. This connection would enable us to effortlessly access extensive information whenever needed. Additionally, it could enhance memory retention by capturing and replaying memories. Furthermore, it could mitigate the loss of memories due to aging by facilitating the uploading of memories onto an AI system stored in the cloud, ensuring their preservation.

Higher Quality of Life for People with Disabilities. Neuralink holds the promise of enhancing the lives of individuals with disabilities. It enables paralyzed individuals to regain control of their bodies, restores sight to the blind, and facilitates hearing for the deaf.

Improved Human-AI Communication and Collaboration. This advancement in technology will grant humans the ability to interact directly with machines, eliminating the need for external tools like keyboards or touch screens. Consequently, individuals can manipulate machines without the use of their hands or voice; rather, they can simply rely on their thoughts accessed through a neural implant in their brain.

Better Internet and Device Connectivity. With Neuralink, we anticipate enhanced connectivity between humans and devices, mitigating concerns about sluggish internet speeds or network disruptions in remote regions.

Cons:

Potential for Brain Injury or Infection. One of the primary concerns surrounding Neuralink is the risk of harming brain tissue. Given the brain's sensitivity, even minor injuries can result in permanent damage or death. Incorrect implantation of Neuralink could lead to infections and inflammation in the brain, potentially increasing the risk of developing Alzheimer's disease later in life.

Risk of Abuse and Misuse. Another drawback of Neuralink is its potential for abuse by individuals seeking to control or extract information from others. Likely abusers include governments, security agencies, and institutions aiming to manipulate individuals or corporations seeking to invade privacy by accessing personal communications and thoughts, posing new cybersecurity threats.

Limited Research on the Long-Term Effects of BCIs. Neuralink's technology could significantly impact the human brain and body, with effects ranging from positive to negative or even dangerous. However,

research into the long-term effects of brain-computer interfaces (BCIs) on humans remains scarce. This lack of research hampers understanding of potential side effects.

Privacy Invasion. Neuralink raises concerns about privacy invasion by accessing thoughts and memories. Implanting the chip allows anyone with access to potentially read thoughts and memories, enabling governments or private entities to monitor individuals without their consent.

Potential Negative Consequences Such as Addiction, Anxiety, or Depression. BCIs pose a risk of addiction if users become reliant on accessing superhuman abilities. This addiction may lead to disengagement from real-life experiences, causing feelings of inadequacy and potentially leading to suicide if access to neural implants is restricted.

High Cost of BCI Technology. BCI devices, including Neuralink, are often prohibitively expensive for most individuals. Neuralink's advanced hardware is expected to be particularly costly compared to other products on the market.

Challenges in Removing or Repairing BCIs. There is a risk of BCIs failing without viable repair options. Insertion of electrodes into brain tissue can cause damage, while implants may lead to scarring and subsequent health issues if not addressed appropriately.

Its Future

Overall, Neuralink's future is brimming with possibilities but also uncertainties. The technology has the potential to revolutionize healthcare, communication, and our understanding of the human brain. However, significant technical hurdles, ethical considerations, and potential social impacts need to be addressed before widespread adoption becomes a reality.

Conclusion

Neuralink isn't aiming for mind-reading quite yet, but their brain-computer interfaces (BCIs) are ambitious. Imagine directly controlling robotic limbs for people with paralysis or communicating with others through brain signals, all without needing phones or computers. While this futuristic tech is still in its early stages, it's already captured the interest of investors and potential users. If Neuralink pulls it off, the impact on society could be revolutionary. But, like any powerful technology, there are potential risks that need careful consideration before widespread use.

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